

THE RURAL PRESS FOR COMMUNITY MOBILIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT IN AKWAIBOM STATE

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Abstract

The adjective “rural” to the average Nigerian conjures up images of some remote address – a people grappling with underdevelopment, hunger, illiteracy and malnutrition. The young and the old - men and women – engaged in menial jobs, petty trade and small scale, subsistence farming. The backwardness of these areas tends to have been exacerbated by the neglect of Nigerian mainstream media, which are urban-based. This neglect has created two track societies: the haves and the have-nots, the rich and the poor, those who have access to the city media and those who have not. Such urban-centered media – print or broadcast – are incapable of responding to the multifarious needs of the rural communities, and bridge the perceived information gaps. This chasm has fueled the assumption that Nigeria's

yawning underdevelopment is a consequence of the failure of the media to sufficiently mobilise the ruralists for development endeavours. A more desirable option is the rural press – created for the reporting of the rural people, by the rural people, and for the people, which would offer greater power and control, conscientisation, empowerment and self-reliance. By problematising urban media neglect this way, this paper advocates that a press that is rural in every respect will engender greater participation, guarantee more dialogical and transactional communication, and, in the long run, address the current lopsided rural reportage, and explore mobilisation strategies that have been tried and proven elsewhere, for the development of rural Nigeria.

Keywords: Press, Rural, Development, Mobilisation, Participation, Community, Media

Introduction

Against popular presumptions, communication comes before food, clothing and shelter as the most basic need of man. While man can evidently live for days without food, clothing and shelter, no man can survive an hour without communication taking place within him (intrapersonal communication), with others (interpersonal communication), with groups of persons (public communication), with large, heterogeneous audiences (mass communication), or even in forms like prayers, dreams, divination, telepathy, exorcism, or necromancy (extra-mundane communication). This notion of the indispensability of communication is what Paul Watzlawick (1967), an Australian-American philosopher and theoretician, together with Janet Bavelas and Don Jackson, in the first of their five Axioms of Communication, communicated in the famous maxim: “One cannot not communicate”. Communication is at the heart of all human intercourses and has been identified as a major force for the improvement of the living conditions of humans in all parts of the world.

Since the second half of the 20th century, the world has witnessed a revolution in the information and communication space that surpasses even the most optimistic prognostication of media futurologists such as Marshall McLuhan, Lewis Mumford and Harold Innis. McLuhan's 'global village' age had since

been attained and the world had since been ushered into what Yergin and Stanislaw (1998) described as “conditions of globality”. But globalization, defined loosely as the spread of products, services, information, ideas, cultures, technologies, developments, etc., around the globe regardless of temporal or spatial location, came not without some consequences. One of such consequences has been the imbalance in the spread of the aforementioned 'global items of value' between the developed North and the developing or underdeveloped South. It was the need to address such imbalance that informed the setting up of the Sean MacBride Commission in December 1977 (MacBride, 1980).

Regrettably, the recommendations of the Sean MacBride's Commission have not been able to solve the imbalance as there is still a plethora of problems in the flow of information and other global items of value. Today, in Southern bloc countries of Africa, Asia and North America, urban cities are doing to rural areas what the Northern bloc did to Southern bloc in the 1970's. In the words of Akpor (2013), the media content of Nigeria and all other countries in the Southern bloc are still being dominated with happenings in their major cities at the detriment of the rural areas. This has not meant well for the Nigerian rural populace who now feel alienated from happenings within their own country.

As succeeding governments at various levels (Federal, State and Local) battle to drive development down to the people, there is now a consensus amongst stakeholders in the development value chain on the criticality of the media as potent vehicles for mobilizing the people towards the attainment of a better life. For instance, General Ibrahim Babangida, Nigeria's former Military Head of State, as cited in Akinfeleye (1993) opined;

No self-sustaining development can take place in Nigeria without the masses of our people being effectively mobilized, genuinely motivated and properly organized for productive activity within the context of freedom, orderly progress and social justice.

In Nigeria, the mainstream media have been reasonably engaged for various purposes, including the mobilization of the people towards development. But

the mainstream media have focused more on matters of national politics, macroeconomics, urban insecurity, city mishaps, celebrity gossips, and other contemporary contents of metropolitan appeal, with little or no attention to the peculiar development needs of rural communities. And since development is a participatory process and the non-city dwellers have not been adequately mobilized through the mass media to participate in the process, passed development efforts have been preoccupied with the promotion of an urban-based strategy of building a modern society aimed at stimulating economic growth. While some achievements may have been recorded in that direction, the unfortunate consequence has been a neglect of the development needs, potentials and aspirations of the rural areas.

It was in a bid to address the problem of rural community neglect associated with mainstream media coverage that the concept of community media was evolved. Community media, according to Anaeto and Solo-Anaeto (2010), are channels of communication owned and managed by the community members. Onabajo (2002) further explains that community media are adaptations of the media for use by the community, for whatever purposes the community decides. They are media in which the community members participate as planners, producers, performers and audience.

The rural press, which can come in the form of rural community newspapers or magazines, is an offspring of community media. The rural press is a publication owned and put together by a rural community to meet its communication and information needs. It seeks to serve and advance the interest of the community where it operates. It serves as the alternative medium through which the development needs and aspirations of the rural community are accentuated and attended to.

Akwa Ibom State has 31 Local Government Areas, with only a few settlements in the entire state qualified to be called urban centers. This implies that a vast majority of the Akwa Ibom geographical mass is rural and in dire need of development. Therefore, the preoccupation of this paper is to examine the rural press as a tool for community mobilization and development within the socio-

cultural construct, concept and context of Akwa Ibom State.

Rural Press, Community Mobilization and Development

The rural press has been defined as a publication of the rural people, by the rural people and for the rural people. Kasoma in Oso (2003) defines it as “a regular publication which carries news stories, features, editorials, illustrations and/or pictures as well as advertisements for rural people”. The rural press serves as an instrument for the propagation of information, education, entertainment, socialization, etc. among inhabitants of a rural community.

The concept of a community can be viewed from two perspectives: geography and psychology. From the geographical perspective, a community is a group of people living together in a particular geographical location and doing things in common. Viewing from the psychological prism, a community would appear as a group of people connected by shared or similar interests, characteristics and values, who may not necessarily be living together. Shorinola (2004) defines it as “a population of people living within legally established limits where the people have some social, cultural and economic features in common which enable them to pursue common goals”.

The persuasive and convincing effort aimed at getting people involved in an organized manner in the execution of a project or programme by equipping them with necessary knowledge and attitude required for participation. It entails using good communication strategies in appealing to people in a convincing manner to adopt a particular pattern in approaching an issue or to accept a cause. People need to be convinced before they can willingly participate in accomplishing a task. Mobilization, in the words of Umechukwu (2004), refers to "all efforts and means legitimately employed to encourage, ginger and get the people ready to take actions aimed at achieving the goals and aspirations of society”.

The term “development” simply refers to a change process that seeks to better the life and environment of man largely through his own effort and at his own pace. According to Dudley Sears (cited in Nwabueze, 2005), development involves the creation of opportunities for the realization of human potentials. It

is the sum total or the outcome of efforts made by the people to improve upon their conditions of living. A society is said to be moving towards development when there is more freedom, more social justice and there are opportunities for the people to participate in taking decisions that affect them (Asemah, 2011). It is a participatory process of social change in a society, intended to bring about both social and material advancement, including greater equality, freedom and other valued qualities for the majority of people, through their gaining greater control over the environment. Development is a continuous process of enabling people to improve their quality of life and beautify their living conditions through positive change, spiritual, material and infrastructural transformation by mobilizing their resources continuously.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is built on the foundation of two theories, namely the agenda-setting theory and the development media.

The agenda-setting theory of the press, as posited by McCombs and Shaw (1972), postulates that the media may not always be successful at telling people what to think, but they are quite successful at telling people what to think about. The basic assumption of the theory is that the media are powerful enough to set the agenda for the public to follow. The theory holds that most of the pictures we store in our heads, most of the things we think or worry about, most of the issues we discuss, are based on what we have read, listened to or watched in different mass media.

The theory further posits that the amount of attention given to an issue in the press affects the level of importance assigned to that issue by the mass media audience. Agenda setting is a media effect theory whose main thrust is that though the media may not change a person's point of view on a particular issue, it may change the person's perception of what is important (Agbo and Fab-Ukozor, 2000).

By the same token, the mass media could place in the consciousness of people in a community developmental issue which require their attention. The media could do this by frequent reportage or coverage of development news and issues that affect the people and the society in general. That way, these issues

discussed by the mass media will become prominent and get prioritized by the people and the government of the people, thereby inspiring or activating community development in the direction of the issues raised.

Specifically, the Agenda-setting theory explains the fact that since the mass media (mainstream or community media) have a duty in setting the agenda for public attention, the rural press in Akwa Ibom State has the capability to inspire development in Akwa Ibom communities by promoting the development needs and aspirations of the people and mobilizing rural communities in the state towards seeking the attainment of better living conditions. It therefore behooves on the operators and would-be operators of the rural press in Akwa Ibom State to see to the effective deployment of this capability in the interest of development.

The development media theory which is hinged on the perception of the press as a potent instrument that can be used to achieve positive development in any society, originated by the UNESCO International Commission for the Study of Communication Problems. The basic tenets of the theory, according to McQuail (1987), are:

That the media should carry out positive development task in line with nationally established policy; freedom of the media should be open to restrictions according to economic priorities and development needs of society; the media in developing countries should align their interests with news and information in other developing countries that are close geographically, culturally and politically; media operations could be restricted to the interest of development in the state.

The Development Media Theory holds that the media have a role to play in facilitating the process of development in developing countries (Asemah,

2011). The media are to be used to serve the general good of the nation. These, the media can do by functioning as government instruments for achieving economic growth, political growth, cultural development and social change in any community; thus, the theory implies that the media should be used to complement government's efforts by carrying out programmes that will lead to positive behavioural change among the people.

The theory which is often seen as the combination of Libertarian and Social Responsibility theories, is anchored on communication for development where the media are seen as reliable tools that can be used to champion social, economic, political, educational and cultural development. It is opposed to dependency and foreign domination and to arbitrary authoritarianism. By implication, the Development Media Theory relates to this study as it explains the necessity for the rural press to be utilized as an efficacious vehicle that can drive sustainable development to the people of Akwa Ibom State. If rural communities in Akwa Ibom State truly desire the attainment of political growth, social change and cultural development, there is need to adopt rural press as a viable tool for community mobilization and development.

The Concept of Community Development

The concept of community development stems from the idea that for development to be meaningful and sustainable, the people must see the need for the development and take steps towards actualizing it. Rendered differently, community development appertains to the active involvement of community members in issues and problems that affect their lives with a view to addressing them. The United Nations Economic and Social Council in 1956, according to Odedeji (2003), defined community development as; The process by which the efforts of the people themselves are united with those of the governmental authorities to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of the communities; to integrate these communities into the life of a nation and to enable them to contribute fully to national progress.

Nwabueze (2005) captured it slightly differently as “a process of improving not just lives of the people of a locality and their ability to utilize resources

available to them in improving their locality, and also the betterment of the interaction processes and forces that shape coexistence in the given society. It is a structured intervention that gives communities greater control over conditions that affect their lives.

Community Development is referred to by some authors as Rural Development. For instance, while Anaeto and Solo-Anaeto (2010) present Rural Development as “a planned process of change designed to alleviate poverty, increase productivity and improve the conditions of the rural areas”, Asemah (2011) simplifies it as “the actions and initiatives taken to improve the standard of living in non-urban neighborhoods, countryside and remote villages. It is a planned process of change which is ultimately designed to reduce the level of poverty, sicknesses and reliance on government in the rural areas. It is a system that entails the utilization of various strategies to bring about development in the rural areas. It involves the creating of awareness to help people of a community identify and assess their own needs and problems, teaching the people knowledge and skills to cope with the problems and instilling in them the determination to take actions to address their problems.

The objectives of every community development endeavour include: to empower with skills and knowledge individuals and group of individuals within a community to engage in development activities, to mobilize community people for social action, to enhance community spirit among community members, to develop responsible local leadership and to inspire active and sustainable development in communities. Onibokun and Faniran (1995) posit that community development thrives on seven elements. They stated the elements as: Initiative, Felt Needs, Self-Help, Citizen Participation, Educational Organ, Local Leadership and Personnel or Change Agents. Community Development is never a destination; rather, it is a process. To successfully execute community development programs, a number of steps are involved. Shirinola (2004) in Anaeto and Solo-Anaeto (2010) highlights the steps involved in the community development process as follows:

- Identification of a small group of leaders or interest groups who can serve as motivators;

- Informational social survey i.e., the fact-finding and identification of community needs/problems;
- Identification of immediate community problems;
- Definition of problems and definition of needs i.e., taking critical analysis of the problems;
- Sharing of identified problems with community leaders;
- Securing citizens' commitment to the programme and identification of needed resources;
- Appraisal of available internal resources and identification of external aid or assistance where necessary;
- Formulation of a detailed plan of action including the timetable;
- Carrying out the action and evaluation of the entire process and results; and
- Identification of derived problems or needs and planning for the continuation of the process.

Rural-Urban Development Inequalities in Akwa Ibom State

Akwa Ibom State is one of the 36 states in Nigeria, situated within the geo-political zone of South-South Nigeria and the geo-economical region of the Niger Delta. Lying between Latitudes 4°32 and 5°33 North and Longitudes 7°35 and 8°25 East. The state is bounded on the East by Rivers State, on the West by Cross River State, on the North by Abia State and on the South by the Gulf of Guinea. With the annual growth rate of the population projected at 3.4%, a recent population projection suggests that about 7,000,000 people are resident in the State. Akwa Ibom State falls within the tropical zone with a dominant vegetation of green foliage of trees and shrubs. The Atlantic coastline stretches 129Km from Oron in the East to Ikot Abasi in the West. The National Population Commission (NPC, 1998) puts the total land area at 6,187_{Km}² which represents 0.67% of the total land mass of Nigeria.

Akwa Ibom State is a major oil producing state and thus, contributes significantly to the total revenue base of the nation. According to data from the NPC (2007), Akwa Ibom State is the second most densely populated State in the Niger Delta with an average population density as high as 634 persons per

kilometer square. Interestingly, about 87.9% of the population in the state is rural. The State has 31 Local Government Areas, with Uyo, Eket, Ikot Ekpene, Abak, Etinan, Ikot Abasi and Oron being the most developed urban centres. This further shows that a significant majority of the State's land spaces are home to rural dwellers.

Development scholars such as Ajala, et al. (2005) and Olayiwola (2005), as cited in Akpan and Atser (2010), have asserted that one of the major factors responsible for low level of rural development is the imbalance in infrastructure distribution. In Akwa Ibom State, preliminary investigation has indicated that the level of rural development is indisputably low, although the pattern of rural development from the perspective of social infrastructure distribution has not been substantially established. Apparently, there is need for more research in this direction.

The issue of regional inequalities is very common in developing countries, but the problem of disparity in development among nations and among the different regions of any nation, according to Akpan (2000) and Antai (2011), is not only restricted to developing countries. Regional inequalities become most disturbing when they degenerate into wide-scale imbalances which keep sections of a geographical whole far behind other sections in terms of the basic conditions of live and livelihood. The problem of development in Nigeria today is multi-faceted, multi-dimensional, and in Oyebanji's (1986) words, a "coat of many colours"

Inequality in the distribution of development activities across various geographical units within a State can result in wide-spread imbalances in socioeconomic fortunes between the rural and the urban settlements. The dynamics of development in Akwa Ibom State can be assessed looking at the interdependence of the level and pace of urbanization in relation to indicators of socio-economic development. Despite impressive progress made in economic development, inequality still characterizes the pattern of socio-economic development in Akwa Ibom State (Umoren, 2013). Spatial inequalities are directly associated with access to virtually all products and services e.g., health, education, roads, housing, infrastructure, etc.

Since 1999 when the present era of democracy began in Nigeria, Akwa Ibom State has witnessed significant development in various spheres. However, it is safe to submit that all parts of the State have not experienced the same dose of development. And if the perceived development inequality would ever be address, the marginalized rural communities must elect to stand up and be counted. They must mobilize themselves towards addressing their development needs and meeting their development aspirations as a people. The rural press has so much to offer in amplifying their voices in this regard.

The Concept of Community Media

For the most part, communication is aimed at bringing about positive change in the audience. But the modern mass media can bring about little or no positive change in the rural communities, principally because they are urban-oriented in content, context, interest and appeal. The modern mass media hardly consider the peculiarities and proclivities of the rural populace as they gather, process and disseminate information to their mass, large and heterogenous audience members. It is this lacuna that community media aspire to close.

Community Media are any form of media that function in service of a community. It is the rise of all kinds of alternative, oppositional, participatory and collaborative media practices that have developed in the journalistic context of 'community media,' 'we media,' 'citizens media,' 'grassroot journalism' or any radical alternative to online and offline mainstream journalistic practices (Deuze, 2006). In other words, it is having access to or creating local alternatives to mainstream media, like local community newspapers, radio stations, or magazines. Community Media aid in the process of building citizenship and raising social awareness. Community media are often given parameters when being defined by groups, but often challenges these boundaries with their broad yet narrow structure.

UNESCO (2011), as cited by www.wikipedia.com, defined Community Media as a distinct sector of the media for their independence base in civil society and provision of a social service as opposed to seeking profits. They serve as a third sector of the media apart from private and public media and are important in giving communities a platform to express their concerns for local issues, engaging in democratic debate and delivering a reliable access to information. Community Media are channels of communication owned and managed by the community members with the primary aim of providing communication and information access to rural and isolated people. Onabajo (2002) explains that community media are adaptations of the media for use by the community, for whatever purposes the community decides. They are media in which the community members participate as planners, producers and audience.

While there is no consensus on the definition of community media as each region displays unique forms, there are common observable elements which give certain media outfits the outlook of community media. Anaeto and Solo-Anaeto (2010) outline such characteristics to include:

- Local/community ownership and management;
- Localized contents and programming;
- Decentralized and democratized media;
- Participatory and interactive;
- Non-profit oriented;
- Limited coverage or reach; and
- Appropriate and indigenous materials and resources.

Community media generally operate on the fundamental principles of access, participation, localism and volunteerism. The contents of community media are basically geared towards development and may include news and articles about development (e.g., health, environment, agriculture, sanitation), information and enlightenment programmes, culturally relevant entertainments (e.g., drama, songs, indigenous stories), as well as community messages (e.g., marriages, naming ceremonies, union meetings, goodwill messages by and to community members).

It is important to accentuate that community media can take any or all of the forms of other conventional media such as print (newspaper, magazines, pamphlets, etc.), radio, television, community-viewing centres, web-based and mixed media. But the commonest forms of community media are the rural radio and the rural press.

The Rural Press: A Potent Form of Community Media

In journalism, the term “Press” is either used to mean “print-based media of mass communication” or “a combination of the print-based media of mass communication and the journalists who operate them”. While types of print materials deployed in development communication include posters (a one-sheet printed paper with text and pictures), leaflets (folded printed papers giving information on a subject), booklet (a printed publication with large number of pages), flip chart (a cardboard or cloth with pictures and messages), newspaper (unbounded printed papers conveying news and other information of news value), magazine, etc., the press, as used in this study, appertains more to newspaper.

According to Asemah (2011), a rural newspaper is a publication for and by the rural people, containing news, views and advertisements for rural community. It is a publication compiled, printed and published in the locality which it is meant to serve and typically published in a language spoken by the majority of the people for whom it is published. It is a publication owned, managed and put together by a rural community to meet its communication needs. It reflects community issues, affairs and events. It keeps the community members abreast of news and information within and outside their own community. It highlights the needs of the community and depicts the joys, problems, culture, as well as the general lives of the rural people.

Caleb (2005) in Ciboh, Nwanwene and Keghku (2005) notes that the rural press is the epitome of journalism that cultivates friendly relations with community readers. It offers much in employment, income and service while stimulating through actions on projects and issues that are development-oriented. The rural press is a potent form of community media in that: It can build comradeship and confidence in the community readers; It can facilitate

convenient contact between producers and consumers within the community; it can stimulate community thinking on local problems and projects; it can guard people's interest and defend their rights; it allows for full participation of community members; it has the ability to localize and domesticate global development concerns to suit the needs of the community where it operates; it can also stimulate a community to embrace development initiatives by mirroring the outcomes of similar initiatives in other climes.

Asemah (2011) outlines the role of the rural press and styled rural newspapers as follows:

1. **Setting Agenda:** A rural newspaper sets the agenda not only for the community, but also the central government regarding what development issues planners in the metropolis should consider.
2. **Promoting literacy:** It contributes to developing literacy among rural people, as it helps the people to consistently practise the act and art of reading and writing.
3. **Providing functional knowledge:** A rural newspapers can be used as platforms to share functional knowledge required in society. Mothers, for instance, can learn about housekeeping, child care, food preparation, disease prevention, etc.
4. **Promoting useful change:** It can serve as a tool to mobilize the people to advocate for and pursue the change they desire. It is not just a shopping list of what the community wants but a tool to inspire all sectors of community towards self-development.
5. **Linking the leader and the people:** A rural newspaper is a channel of mutual communication between the rulers and the ruled.
6. **Serving as window to the world:** The rural newspaper serves as a window to the 'outside world' to enable it to see the life of the village community and possibly render help where possible.
7. **Safeguarding cultural identity:** The participatory rural newspaper plays an important role in safeguarding, conserving and promoting practices which are useful to the rural community so as to maintain their identity.

Rural Press, Rural Mobilization and Community Development in Akwa Ibom State

Though there are impressive efforts geared towards improving the living conditions of people in the various geographical units of Akwa Ibom state, the socioeconomic development strides in Akwa Ibom State, like most other states of developing nations, are not evenly distributed in all areas. Umoren (2013) notes that “Despite impressive progress made in economic development, inequality still characterizes the pattern of socio-economic development in Akwa Ibom State. Spatial inequalities are directly associated with access to virtually all products and services e.g., health, education, roads, housing, infrastructure, etc.”

The living conditions of the people in the interior communities of Akwa Ibom State are troubling enough to instigate genuine attempts by the communities towards self-help and self-development. There is a dire need for the efforts of the people of Akwa Ibom State to compliment those of the government to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of their community and sustainably integrate the communities into the life of the state and nation to enable them contribute fully to national progress. There is a dire need for a structured intervention by the communities aimed at giving the people greater control over conditions that affect their lives. There is a dire need to increasingly create awareness to help people in these Akwa Ibom communities to identify and assess their own needs and problems, increasingly teach the people knowledge and skills to cope with the problems and increasingly instill in them the determination to take actions to address their problems. There is a dire need for Community Development in Akwa Ibom State and Akwa Ibom people are alive to this need, though not sufficiently so.

For community development initiative to happen, the people must first be mobilized to participate in the process. Nwodu and Ukozor (2003) cited Udokah as defining mobilization as “the awakening or activation of the dominant consciousness of a greater number of people with the use of views, ideas for the purpose of gaining their support for an action or inaction”. It entails building and sustaining cohesive alliance between development agents

and targets or beneficiaries of a given developmental programme as well as serving their support and participation in the programme. According to Akpor (2013), Rural Mobilization should typically begin with a conscious recognition of the problems to be addressed and must be seen in terms of involving the people in taking part actively and freely in discussions and decisions affecting their general welfare.

In Akwa Ibom State, it cannot be said with surety that the rural communities have been sufficiently mobilized towards participating in the identification of their development needs and towards the attainment of their development aspirations. This is not to say that there has been a complete absence of rural mobilization towards community development in Akwa Ibom State. Various rural communities have adopted various approaches towards mobilizing themselves for the development of their communities. Some of such approaches include the establishment of community unions, the provision of community-funded scholarships to young community folks, the establishment of community-funded schools, hospitals, community centres, the articulation of community needs and subsequent presentation of such needs to governmental authorities, the setting up of rural press and other community media, etc.

The rural press has been identified by a few communities in Akwa Ibom State as a tool for community mobilization and development. In Mkpato Enin Local Government Area, there is a rural newspaper called “*Ikon*”. Though *Ikon* does not tick all the boxes as to what constitute the characteristics of an ideal rural newspaper, it is one of the finest existing examples of a rural newspaper in the state. Though it is not published by the community per se but by a community volunteer (a former Local Government Transition Committee Chairman in Mkpato Enin) by the name Ubong Ekefre who mobilizes other community volunteers for that purpose. *Ikon* is primarily produced by Mkpato Enin people, for Mkpato Enin people and in Mkpato Enin community. The content, context and appeal remain local, with a clear objective to mobilize rural communities in Mkpato Enin towards the development of their areas.

In Abak Local Government Area, there are at least three newspapers that partly fit into the mold of the rural press. They are “*Voice of Abak*” anchored by Isonguyo Iniodu, “*The People of Abak*” anchored by an indigene of Utu Abak that goes by the name Alhaji Aminu (formerly, Mr. Akpaidiok), and “*Abak Chronicles*” jointly anchored by Alhaji Aminu and Ubong Akpan. *Voice of Abak* is the most regularly published and most functional rural press of the three examples in Abak Local Government Area.

From Mkpāt Enin to Abak, to Eastern Obolo, to Udung Uko, to Obot Akara, to Ini, to Ukanafun, to Nsit Atai, to other essentially non-urbanized communities in Akwa Ibom State, the rural press is today still being engaged as a tool – not the only tool, but one of the tools - for community mobilization and development in Akwa Ibom State.

Conclusion and Recommendations

There is no doubt that a nexus exists between rural community development and rural community mobilization. No meaningful and sustainable development can take place in any community without the effective involvement and participation of the people of that community. The rural press, as a form of community media available to the rural people, is one of the tools deployed for community mobilization and development in Akwa Ibom State.

While the rural press is reasonably engaged in some rural communities in Akwa Ibom State for the purpose of community mobilization and development, such engagements are grossly inadequate. Greater development outcomes are possible in Akwa Ibom State if the rural press and other forms of community media can more effectively be deployed in mobilizing local communities towards identifying their development needs and meeting their development aspirations. To this end, this paper advances the following recommendations:

There is need for the establishment of more rural newspapers in Akwa Ibom State. The present trend where hitherto functional rural newspapers are becoming dysfunctional or moribund while new ones hardly come on board, is unwholesome and objectionable. There is need to increasingly create

awareness in non-urban centres on the need for the establishment of more community-owned and community-managed press outfits as homegrown alternatives to urban-based, metropolitan, mainstream media platforms. This will afford the people the opportunity to gain greater control over the circumstances and conditions of their lives and livelihoods.

Existing rural press outfits should do more to reflect the ideals of community media. A rural newspaper should not operate as a distant change agent published by a singular individual who may or may not be a representative of the community people. A rural newspaper needs to be published by the people and be seen as being published by the people, for the people and in the area where the people reside. Since the people are key initiators of community development efforts, they should be part of the communication process that is aimed at gingering them to participate in the development activities. It should have community appeal and seek to improve the total well-being of the people of the community it exists.

There is need to revive interest in community journalism and to (re)train communicators in the area of development communication to constantly keep them abreast with strategies to adopt in mobilizing people for development. It is not enough to have been generally trained as a journalist or to have practised in mainstream mass media; operators of rural newspaper should have the specialized training and skill-sets required for the effective operations of a 21st century rural press.

There is need for further research in this area. This recommendation comes in two prongs. On the one part, volunteer journalists or communities seeking to establish rural press outfits or other community media platforms should first and foremost embark on thorough audience research and needs assessment research before launching into the deep waters of community journalism. As Nwosu (1990) notes, “there is need for audience research before embarking on any communication exercise”. On the second part, there is need for more scholarly researches by development communication experts to examine why the rural press and other forms of community media are increasingly going extinct even in a developing nation like Nigeria. While that concern was

beyond the scope of this paper, it is important that further researches be conducted by future researchers to better understand the challenges and seek ways of addressing them.

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